

First Demonstration of Field Free Switching Perpendicular SOT-MRAM 4kb Array Using Z-Spin

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Abstract—In a fully integrated 300 mm platform for perpendicular Spin-Orbit Torque Magnetoresistive RAM (SOT-MRAM), we demonstrate field-free functionality in a 4kb characterization array. Our results show that a stack design of a ferromagnet (FM) / Ta bilayer track enables Z-Spin based switching on SOT-MRAM devices in the <10ns regime. Furthermore, our devices show tunneling magnetoresistance (TMR) > 90% and retention >10 years, which is comparable to a standard field assisted SOT device. The devices integrated in 4kb sub-bank array configurations show excellent distributions and low variability between dies, paving the way for advanced memory applications of SOT-MRAM.

I. INTRODUCTION

MRAM and other related magnetic tunnel junction (MTJ) technologies have been long-term contenders for realizing improved spintronics applications, including replacements for eFlash memories and candidates for last-level cache memories[1]. The most mature MRAM device, spin transfer torque (STT)-MRAM, still faces challenges related to intrinsic trade-offs in speed and endurance due to a shared write/read circuitry[1]. A promising emerging candidate for memory with cache potential is Spin-Orbit Torque (SOT)-MRAM, which overcomes the trade-offs with a 3-terminal arrangement separating read and write paths[2]. SOT devices have matured in the past few years with demonstrated CMOS array functionality[3,4], BEOL 400°C process compatibility[5] and improved WER in single devices[6], showing their overall potential for higher technology readiness. However, a significant open challenge in SOT-MRAM development is the need of symmetry breaking to enable deterministic write operation of the memory states, which is conventionally achieved with an external applied field[2]. This field requirement imposes strong technology design constraints on achieving a dense devices integration in an array, and therefore innovations in field-free switching (FFS) solutions to the write operation are very desirable. Table 1 summarizes the current state of the art proposals for FFS SOT devices, with different key approaches currently at different stages of assessment and maturity. Each choice of FFS mechanism imposes its own set of challenges as the SOT component is built-in differently for each implementation. Approaches such as combining STT and SOT[7] and embedding a magnetic hard mask as a proxy for applied field[8] show promising results, however, significant challenges remain in integrating these solutions into a CMOS array. Another class of FFS

systems are in-plane MTJs, where the retention is achieved not by interfacial anisotropy but rather by the shape anisotropy of an elliptical MTJ volume[3]. While successfully demonstrated in a CMOS setup[3], perpendicular systems remain attractive due to the readily compatible integration and scalability of MTJs not relying on shape anisotropy. Recently, a promising approach is the use of the Z-Spin effect, which introduces an intrinsic symmetry breaking component to the standard SOT device configuration[9] by either introducing a ferromagnetic/nonmagnetic (FM/NM) stack or a geometrical asymmetry such as a wedge or exotic crystalline lattices. So far, this method has mostly been demonstrated in Hallbar experiments or simplified structures[9]. In this work we demonstrate for the first time fully functional SOT-MRAM devices integrated in a 300mm wafer CMOS arrays utilizing the Z-Spin effect of a FM/Ta based stack. We first show how stack design can achieve devices which preserve their standard MRAM properties (TMR, retention) when introducing the Z-Spin generating layers. We then show how such devices integrated into CMOS 4kb sub-banks with variable critical dimensions (CD) of MTJ size and SOT track pitch in a characterization array have good switching distributions and stable metrics across arrays, confirming the potential of the Z-Spin FFS for more advanced SOT-MRAM integration.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Stack design and fabrication of FM/Ta SOT-MRAM

The working principle of the Z-Spin effect is the spin polarization and following diffusion of a spin current with a z-component[10]. In Fig. 1, this process is described in a general FM/NM stack. The spin orbit coupling field \mathbf{B}_{so} is responsible for two effects, first, in the FM/NM interface, spins of a charge current \mathbf{I} are filtered via the Spin Hall Effect (SHE), which also occurs for standard SOT tracks such as Pt and W[2], inducing a diffusion of Y-spins through the NM material, and leads to nondeterministic operation (Fig.1a)). Second, now due to the presence of a magnetization \mathbf{m} in the FM, the charge current is polarized, and its precession around \mathbf{B}_{so} results in a flow of a spin current through the NM layer with a z-component, leading to deterministic operation (Fig.1b)). As a conductive metal having a spin diffusion length >1.5nm, on top of preserving the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA) of the MTJ devices, Ta has been chosen to fabricate FM/Ta based devices[11]. Fig. 2 shows the spin efficiency obtained by hysteresis loop shift measurements at 0Oe applied In-plane (IP) field (measuring the Z-Spin generation efficiency) [12] for different thicknesses of Ta

(denoted by TaX) in a fixed FM/Ta/MTJ configuration, highlighting a maximum efficiency for the Ta3 stack design. Our devices are fabricated in 300mm wafers, with integration into CMOS arrays and single devices similar to previous reports[3], with devices of CD = 63nm MTJ size and 99nm gap selected for the present study. Figs. 3a), b) and c) show the standard metrics of tunneling magnetoresistance (TMR), coercivity and retention have a dependence on the type of FM/Ta stack, with Ta3 retaining good properties with best spin generation efficiency. Likewise, Fig. 3d) shows a representative magnetoresistive loop of a fabricated Ta3 device demonstrating the FM/Ta/MTJ configuration does not degrade the MTJ properties. In Fig. 4a) we demonstrate the single device FFS, where for each applied IP field point, we calculate the switching probability of a device for N=100 voltage sweeping cycles. For large enough IP applied fields of either polarity there is either a dominance of the SHE from Ta (Fig. 4b), c)) or a competition with the Z-Spin effect leading to a reduction in switching, with once again a peak in switching probability at 0 IP applied field, which is the FFS regime (Fig. 4d)). Fig. 4e) shows a TEM cross section of a single device confirming the FM/Ta track structure.

B. FFS SOT-MRAM in a 4kb CMOS array

The FM/Ta3/MTJ stack is integrated into 4kb CMOS sub-bank arrays in two types of devices[3], namely standard and extreme types, shown in Figs. 5a), b). Figs 5c), d) show SEM images of each type. In the extreme case, the width of the FM/Ta SOT track is scaled to the CD of the MTJ preventing waste of charge current, for all the spin generated in the cross section of Fig. 5b) flows towards the MTJ. Furthermore, extreme devices have a scaled pitch in between tracks of 99nm (Fig. 5d)). The integration process shows a better yield of extreme devices (Fig. 6a)), with a tighter distribution and less shorting observed in the parallel or low resistance (R_p) vs TMR profile. Fig. 6b) details the distributions of the R_p and antiparallel or high (R_{ap}) resistances of extreme Ta3 devices in a 4kb sub-bank array (N = 1 die). The distributions are well separated by over 8 standard deviations and showcase the successful integration of the FM/NM/MTJ stack design. The extreme 4kb sub-bank array devices also show good statistical reproducibility. In Fig. 6c) we can see the overlapping distributions of R_p and R_{ap} for 28 dies (112kb points) around the center of a 300mm wafer. First, we note the medians of each die distribution as well as their separation (reflected in the TMR) correspond very well to each other. Moreover, the standard deviation and confidence intervals following from the overlapping distributions show good coherence with only slight impact in the R_p and R_{ap} separation in comparison to each single die. The normal quantile plot from Fig. 6c) also shows the consistency of device yield, with $\leq 5\%$ of the total overlapped distributions having a resistance significantly deviated from the median value towards shorting. The R_p , R_{ap} window across dies can be further improved with optimizations to the patterning process targeting short reduction. Fig. 7 shows the full demonstration of FFS functionality using the extreme Ta3 stack devices in a 4kb sub-bank array. To record the switching statistics, controlled

switching experiments were performed by initializing the state applying perpendicular magnetic field (“Set”) before performing the electrical switching at 5ns (“Reset”). The switching rates in Figs. 7a), c) show that for the 4kb sub-bank array similar switching properties to the single device cycling are obtained with mostly $\geq 75\%$ switching rates. Further confirmation of the FFS Z-Spin is demonstrated by saturating the FM layer magnetization in opposite polarity, resulting in a change of the switching polarity in Figs. 7b), d). Note that the switching probability of the fabricated Ta3 devices reaches up to 90% in single devices as evidenced by the average loop of Fig. 4d), which is further reduced in the CMOS array where device variability is added. Further improvements to our proof of concept can be made to target better functionality of the array devices. Table 2 shows the tuning knobs of the Z-Spin effect[9]. With optimization of the patterning process to target a well defined magnetization \mathbf{m} of the FM, a choice of NM materials with large spin diffusion coefficients, as well as balancing the relative resistivities of the FM/NM stack to ensure a major flow of charge current through the FM layer, Z-Spin devices with enhanced properties can be integrated for improved array functionality.

In conclusion, we have successfully demonstrated through stack design of FM/Ta/MTJ systems that the Z-Spin FFS integrated into a 300mm platform can preserve standard MTJ properties. A clear pathway towards functionality improvement is possible via tuning knobs of the FM/NM track. Furthermore, with Z-Spin devices integrated into a 4kb CMOS array, we can achieve good statistical properties and device functionality while removing the in-plane applied field during SOT-MRAM operation. This is an important milestone that fulfills the FFS pre-requisite in considering SOT-MRAM as a strong contender for advanced memory technology applications.

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FFS Method					
Scalability	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Array Demo	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Retention	Perpendicular	Perpendicular	Perpendicular	Perpendicular	In-plane
I/O Mechanism	TMR	TMR	TMR	Hallbar	TMR

Table 1. Comparison of state-of-the-art approaches to Field-Free Switching (FFS) of SOT-MRAM devices, with regards to application stage, scalability and read/write.

Figure 1. Working principle of Z-Spin devices, with a) standard Y-Spin generation mechanism of SOT, and b) Z-Spin generation mechanism from spin polarization of current I .

Figure 2. Z-Spin efficiency as function of FM/Ta track design in fabricated devices, at 0 Oe applied field in the x-direction.

Figure 3. a) TMR, b) Coercivity and c) Retention of MTJ devices in different FM/Ta designs (54 devices/type). d) representative MTJ behavior of single device (field in the z-direction).

Figure 4. Single device Z-Spin effect confirmation from dependence of applied field in the x-direction. a) Switching probability of device for N=100 voltage sweeps per field point. b) Average loop for N=100 cycles from positive field polarity. c) Average loop for N=100 cycles from negative field polarity. d) Average loop from Z-Spin effect (0 IP field). e) TEM cross section of single device showing FM/Ta track.

Figure 5. Array properties of FM/Ta3 stack devices. **a) b)** standard and extreme device types, with 18nm and 0nm width margin respectively. **c)** SEM image of standard devices, with 215nm side gap. **d)** SEM image of extreme devices with 99nm side gap.

Figure 6. Collective statistics of MTJ devices in 4kb sub-bank arrays of a 300mm wafer fabricated with the FM/Ta3 stack type. **a)** TMR vs R_p (low resistance) in standard vs extreme devices for $N=1$ die. **b)** Statistics of low and high resistance states in extreme devices of $N=1$ die. **c)** Statistics of extreme devices in $N=28$ dies with normal quantiles.

Figure 7. 4kb sub-bank array switching using Z-Spin ($B_x = 0\text{Oe}$) at 5ns pulses, with set/reset distributions and switching rates across 4kb devices per switching operation. **a) b)** Parallel set to Antiparallel reset operation under different magnetization polarities of FM material in FM/Ta3 stack. **c) d)** Antiparallel set to Parallel reset operation under different magnetization polarities of FM material in FM/Ta3 stack.

Spin polarization	Spin diffusion	Transmission vs reflection
Current spin polarization dependent on IP magnet (e.g Co, NiFe, CoFe)	High spin diffusion length for materials with low spin Hall angle (e.g Ta, Ti, Cu)	Transmission or reflection of spin current dependent on relative resistance of NM and FM layers

Table 2. Tuning Knobs for efficient Z-Spin generation, including spin polarization, spin diffusion and transmission coefficients of FM/NM material candidates.